

5GMediaHUB QoS/QoE Monitoring Engine

Apostolos Siokis*, Kostas Ramantas*, George Margetis†, Stefania Stamou†, Ryan McCloskey‡, Martin Tolan‡, Christos Verikoukis*±

* Iquadrat Informatica S.L, Barcelona, Spain

† Institute of Computer Science Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas, Heraklion, Greece

‡ South East Technological University, Waterford, Ireland

± University of Patras, Patras, Greece

Email: a.siokis@iquadrat.com, kramantas@iquadrat.com, gmarget@ics.forth.gr, stefstamou@ics.forth.gr, Ryan.McCloskey@WaltonInstitute.ie, Martin.Tolan@WaltonInstitute.ie, cveri@upatras.gr

Abstract— 5G provides significantly faster data transfer speeds compared to previous generations of wireless networks. However, 5G networks present several challenges to media application developers. To this end, 5GMediaHUB project creates a high-level abstraction layer between media applications and the underlying 5G infrastructure. One of the components within the 5GMediaHUB platform is the Quality of Service/Quality of Experience Monitoring Engine. The QoS/E engine is utilised to perform monitoring of the performance of all of the test attributes (that is the individual components that together comprise the entire application executing at different points/layers within the experimentation framework). This allows for the ease of monitoring as the various monitoring managers are essentially agnostic of the application under test and are purely driven by the associated test configuration data associated with the application. This provides for a testing platform that is easily extended with little to no modification required as new applications are added to the portfolio within the experimentation platform. Moreover, this engine is leveraged for Video quality assessment (VQA) to measure video quality, leveraging on objective methods to essentially predict the Quality of Experience (QOE), i.e., how the video quality will be perceived by end users.

Keywords—5G, QoS, QoE, QoE prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

5GMediaHUB project [1] creates a high-level abstraction layer between media applications and the underlying 5G infrastructure, enabling them to have a simplified but sufficient abstracted visibility (i.e. view of the network corresponding to a specific network slice) of the infrastructure state for network-wide control and resource management, so as to be able to dynamically deploy, orchestrate and manage their services through elastic network

slicing, to ensure service and workload isolation. One of the main outputs from the 5GMediaHUB project is the creation and establishment of a 5G experimentation facility that will allow for the development and testing of vertical applications specifically for the media industry. To enable this, the 5GMediaHUB project will create a new experimenter’s platform that provides access and control to underlying 5G testbed infrastructures, while also abstracting the complexities and domain specific knowledge away from the set of media application developers themselves. This experimenter’s platform is composed of several user facing applications and backend services that stand between the user specific domain (media application development) and this platform (5G enabled experimentation platform), thereby reducing complexity in the vertical applications development cycles and accelerating their time to market.

One of the components within the 5GMediaHUB platform is the Quality of Service/Quality of Experience Monitoring Engine (QoE Apps have been proposed in the literature as in [2]). The engine is an innovative component that provides QoS and QoE monitoring and control, leveraging DevOps processes. This engine allows developers to quickly collect data relating to a test execution cycle of their vertical applications & associated NetApps, while also performing an analysis on the performance of those application attributes. The generated results of the testing cycles include the calculation of the overall Quality of Service and the associated Quality of Experience as would be noted by a user consuming the media content in a real-world scenario. The QoS/E Engine also collates all of the relevant data into a report that is then associated with the parameters and artefacts of the test within the experimenter’s portal.

The main aim of this work is to describe the design and implementation of the Quality of Service/Quality of Experience monitoring manager engine. It also describes the sub-components that comprise the QoS/E Engine and covers the methodology relating to the ingress of the raw metric data used in each of those sub-components. The design also includes the architecture for the data processing pipelines used for calculating the quality of service and subsequently the associated quality of experience, to eventually collating all of the results into the component database to be made available for authorized clients.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II provides a description of the overall requirements along with its main sub-components. Section III drills down into each of the sub-components comprising the QoS/QoE Monitoring Engine providing an overview of the processing relating to that component. Section III also provides details relating to the Quality of Experience prediction manager and its proposed design & architecture. Section IV provides an overview of the signalling interface that is used to publish the

Fig 1. 5GMediaHUB Overall Architecture highlighting the QoS/QoE Monitoring Engine

set of input data and the calculated results set to authorised clients.

II. CONTINUOUS QoS/QoE MONITORING ENGINE OVERVIEW

Figure 1 gives an overview of the 5GMediaHUB overall architecture with the QoS/QoE Monitoring Engine highlighted within the “Experimentation Tools” layer with respect to the other components also within the 5GMediaHUB platform. It is located within the platform’s middleware between the 5G testbed (and associated components such as NetApps) below and the experimenter’s portal. This allows for the QoS/QoE engine to potentially

Fig 2. 5GMediaHUB Overall Architecture highlighting the QoS/QoE Monitoring Engine

gain access to the set of raw metrics from each of the main data sources such as the 5G Testbeds, the NetApps and both the vertical applications and User Equipment (UE) which most are required to execute its analysis. The sources of raw metrics made available is dependent upon the use case scenario being executed.

The QoS/E engine can operate in two distinct modes: On-line and Off-line.

In the on-line mode, the QoS/E engine receives its trigger from the experimenter’s portal to begin operation. This is the

main use case for the QoS/E engine and it will operate in parallel with the other components in the 5GMediaHUB platform. The data is ingested in real-time as its produced (and made available to the data collector component) and analysed continuously.

In off-line mode, the QoS/E engine will operate independently of the other components in the 5GMediaHUB framework. In this mode a test cycle is executed and all of the generated data is captured. Once the test cycle is completed the entire data set is then ingested by the QoS/E engine where its analyses is based on the complete dataset for the test cycle.

Figure 2 expands on the QoS/QoE monitoring engine itself which also lists the main actors that interact with the engine.

As can be seen in Figure 2, the main actor is the vertical application developer. They utilise the QoS/E Engine to understand how their application design is performing and if any design or configuration changes are required prior to release of their application. As the main overall goal of any media application is to ensure the satisfaction of the end users that consume the media products, it is important to guarantee that the delivery of the media is as stable and reliable as possible. This is best determined by monitoring the Quality of Experience for the users.

Figure 2 also captures the main virtual actors in the form of the Experimenters Portal. It is from this portal that the user will initiate a test run execution where all of the data capture, analysis, monitoring and results will be contextualized in order to generate an overall report relating to that test run execution cycle. The Experimenters Portal also provides access to the Data Collector where all of the metric data is collected during a test cycle. The QoS/E engine will ingest the required raw data for analysis from the data collector component.

As with the other 5GMediaHUB engines and components the User Management Module (UMM) is utilised to provide centralised user access and authentication which is especially important when testing new vertical specific applications and NetApps that may have a potential

Fig 3. Metrics Ingress from platform components into the QoS/QoE Engine

commercial impact. As the overall experimentation facility is open to multiple developers, designers and component providers it is important that proprietary information (designs, code, etc.) can remain private. The UMM provides this functionality across the entire set of 5GMediaHUB platform applications, components and engines.

As results are generated within the engine itself the “KPIs – API Endpoint” module provides the ability for application developers to programmatically retrieve results from the QoS/E engine on a timely basis so that they may implement dynamic adaption to their content in order to ensure that their SLAs are maintained as much as possible.

The QoS/E engine potentially requires raw data input from the following sources in order for it to execute its analysis to determine how the vertical applications and the NetApps are performing: NFVI(s), NetApps, Vertical Applications including the end user’s UEs

III. QoS/QoE ENGINE ARCHITECTURE DESIGN

Examining the internal structure of the QoS/E engine it can be seen that it is mainly composed of three sub-components, each of which are specific to a particular operating plane of the connectivity representing the end-to-end network. Figures 3 and 4 display each of the identified data input streams and their associated handler within the QoS/E engine. It is important to notice that at each layer in the analysis stack, the resulting outputs are only as good as the data that is available to it, therefore in order to generate an overall view of the quality of experience for a user the QoS/E engine must aggregate all of the data streams in an appropriate manner to determine the overall QoE score. The NetApps Monitoring manager sub-component only has visibility of the metrics originating within the NFVIs and the NetApps themselves, therefore results from this component can only be localised to that particular part of the network. The same can be said for the Vertical Application Monitoring manager in that the results generated from this component are only related to the metrics from the vertical applications (including the consumer UEs if available). At a higher level of processing, both data streams (NFVI/NetApps & Verticals) can be aggregated before the overall QoE score can

be determined. Figure 4 captures the relationship between the input data streams, their associated handler and the aggregation of their results for the overall score calculation.

A. NetApp QoS monitoring manager

The primary responsibility of the NetApps QoS monitoring manager is to perform a constant analysis of the various attributes relating to each of the instantiated NetApps that are currently executing within the context of the current test cycle. Each NetApp specifies which attributes have the highest priority and the monitoring engine uses these attributes as part of its analysis. The raw KPIs related to the NetApp under test are requested from the data collector (within the experimenter’s portal module) and are used in the analysis. The results are then generated and stored within the QoS/E database where they can be signaled to the appropriate handler which can be either the vertical application or the NFVI (used as the 5G testbed for the experiment).

Based on the monitoring requirements for each of the individual NetApps, it is proposed that the design of the NetApps QoS monitoring manager can be fulfilled by a single architecture that is generic in nature and agnostic to the actual NetApp(s) being utilised as part of the test execution cycle. This generic architecture, when realized is sufficient for the monitoring needs of all the proposed NetApps. When a test cycle is triggered the monitoring engine will use the set of configured attributes for the NetApps that are executing to extract the set of KPIs that form the monitoring of those NetApps, along with the thresholds and various limits that specify the warning and critical levels. This allows for each NetApp configuration to be customized depending on the nature of the test cycle being executed and the critical nature of the communications required.

These are two main interfaces required for the NetApps QoS monitoring manager:

- Data Collector API for requesting KPIs
- Results storage and signalling to the QoS/E database

Fig 4. QoS/QoE Engine with sub-components responsible for specific metric ingress processing

B. Vertical QoS & QoE monitoring manager

This section covers the design and development of the Vertical QoS & QoE monitoring manager. The Vertical QoS & QoE monitoring manager will estimate end-to-end QoS and QoE related KPIs (e.g. Mean Opinion Score) for media applications via the Media AF APIs and via test servers and UE client software deployed at the access site, to take into account the impact of the RAN.

The architecture of the vertical monitoring manager includes the implementation of a data processing pipeline consisting of several stages where the input data is examined, validated, processed (analysed) and finally reported. The input data is, first of all, examined to detect any missing raw measurements or detect scaling errors that could affect the output of the analysis. Once the first stage is complete the next phase in the pipeline is the analysis of the input data. This stage executes the appropriate algorithms that will determine the performance of the vertical application with respect to the end user perceived quality of service and attempt to infer the resultant quality of experience. The entire

Fig 5. Vertical Monitoring Manager Internal Architecture

analysis pipeline is displayed in Figure 5.

The pre-processing engine is responsible for the initial inspection of the input data and is required to clean-up any anomalies that may be present. It is where the raw input data is cleaned and verified in order to be consumed for analysis by the modelling engine.

1) Features Scaling

This engine applies data mining techniques that involve transforming raw data into an understandable format. Real-world data can often be incomplete, inconsistent, and/or lacking in certain behaviours or trends, and is likely to contain many errors. Data pre-processing is a proven method of resolving such issues. Furthermore, this engine describes any type of processing performed on raw data to prepare it for the next processing procedure. Commonly used as a preliminary data mining practice, data pre-processing transforms the data into a format that will be more easily and effectively processed for the purpose of the user. There are a number of different tools and methods used for pre-processing, this engine performs two main pre-processing tasks, namely: Features Scaling and Data Imputation in addition to reading from and writing to the dataset. Sometimes the input raw data may contain features highly varying in magnitudes, units and range. But since most of the analysis algorithms (such as within machine learning) use Euclidian distance between two data points in their computations, this is a problem. If left alone, these algorithms only take in the magnitude of features neglecting the units. The results would vary greatly between different units, e.g. 100Mb vs 500kb. The features with high magnitudes will weigh in a lot more in the distance calculations than features with low magnitudes. There are

different techniques to perform features scaling, for example but not limited to: standardization, normalization, robust scaling, MaxAbs scaler. Each of those scalars works under certain conditions; thus the scaler is chosen based on the data type and other criteria.

2) Raw Data Imputation

For various reasons, many real-world data streams may suffer from missing values, often encountered as blanks, NaN or other placeholders stating that the data may not be available in time for the analysis to proceed. Such input data streams may be incompatible with the estimators which assume that all values in an input array are numerical, and that all have and hold meaning. A basic strategy to use when dealing with incomplete datasets is to discard entire rows and/or columns containing missing values. However, this comes at the price of losing data which may be valuable (even though incomplete). Another strategy is to impute the missing values, i.e. to infer them from the known part of the data. Missing data introduce an element of ambiguity into data analysis. They can affect properties of statistical estimators such as means, variances or percentages, which could result in a loss of power and potential misleading conclusions. A variety of techniques have been proposed for substituting missing values with statistical prediction, this process is generally referred to as "missing data imputation". Most published articles in this field deal with the development of new imputation methods, however few studies report a global evaluation of existing methods in order to provide guidelines to make the more appropriate methodological choice in practice. Moreover, there are many different algorithms to impute missing data, some of them only work for univariate datasets whereas others work for both univariate and multivariate datasets. Types of missing data can fall into one of the following:

- Missing Completely at Random – MCAR: means there is no relationship between the missingness of the data and any values, observed or missing. There is nothing systematic going on that makes some data more likely to be missing than others.
- Missing at Random – MAR: means there is a systematic relationship between the propensity of missing values and the observed data, but not the missing data. So, for example, if men are more likely to tell you their weight than women, weight is MAR.
- Missing Not at Random - MNAR, means there is a relationship between the propensity of a value to be missing and its values. So, for example, where the people with the lowest education are missing on education.

The QoS/E engine pre-processing component will assume the data are at least missing at random (MAR). The analysis engine phase of the vertical monitoring manager will consider the following assumptions prior to the final design of the QoE analysis engine itself:

- QoE is treated as a decreasing function of QoS: the more the collected QoS is below what user expects then the more the QoE is low, QoE is a function of QoS and user preference
- QoE can take values between 0 (bad experience) to 1 (satisfied user), techniques based on objective video and image quality assessments can be normalized to fit this assumption.

- QoE is the product of QoS contributions from each QoS metric (delay, loss, throughput, accessibility), hence the product of two QoS with values in [0,1] results in a new QoE which values in [0 1] too.

- Functions such as $f(x) = e^{-ax}$ can be proposed as mapping function to describe QoE as function of QoS, parameters of the model reflect how fast QoE decreases if measured QoS is below expected.

- QoE reflects user perception, therefore, users may provide their evaluation after averaging the instantaneous values of QoE,

- QoE will be set to the previous QoE recorded or predicted if no transmission occurs, or if the buffer is full and not able to receive more packets.

- We assume that two different records of one QoS metric results in two different QoE.

- QoE of multimedia services can be approximated by normalized PSNR

- User generally is able to provide feedbacks after a long period of service, therefore, the QoE can be the average of elementary QoE (filter process).

As the input metric values are pre-processed, the pipelines facilitate that the metrics are ingested into the analysis engine for calculating the QoS/E. Firstly the engine attempts to cluster various input metrics into clusters that are combined to provide a particular KPI. These KPIs are specific to a particular aspect of the communications channel and the network they are traversing. There are additional KPIs relating to jitter, throughput, bandwidth, etc. and these will be defined in due course with their associated raw metric counters.

These KPIs can then be further distilled to provide aspects of QoS/E that are important such as:

- **Load:** A measure of the computational work ongoing and captures the state of the running processes either using the CPU or in a wait state.

- **Computation:** Can be defined as a combination of certain CPU & Memory attributes which may also be combined with the overall idle profile to characterise an overload or malfunction in the underlying platform.

- **Disk:** Can be used to capture prolonged periods of inefficient IO wait times when the CPU is otherwise idle, can be used to identify potential bottlenecks in the read/write operations associated with the underlying disks.

- **IO:** Captures the latency when interacting with IO devices when there could be, for example, a subbed and prolonged surge in incoming traffic sufficiently greater than the computed average.

Once the KPIs have been transformed from their original metric counters, the analysis engine will then attempt to calculate values for the instantaneous QoS for those KPIs, with a second step attempting to infer the QoE which includes the use of applying user preferences for preference QoE where the resultant score is customized for that user. The outputs of the analysis engine (QoS & QoE scores) are then correlated and reported to the QoS/E Engine DB for storage and publishing (if required). The outputs are also used in the next stage of the overall QoS/E Engine within the “QoE Prediction and Control Manager” module that is detailed below. As the use cases mature more relevant data will be made available to the engine to allow for refinement of the algorithms utilised thus allowing for more accurate

predictions for the future values of QoE based on learned experiences.

For the set of UE specific KPIs the Vertical Monitoring Manager may have to connect directly to the Nomade Live Register (in charge of connecting UEs to the StreamSelector NetApp which is the central point for collecting information both for UEs and the NetApp itself) by using REST API while also exchanging JSON files with it. The Vertical Monitoring Manager will also utilise the data collector of the experimenter’s portal to retrieve the set of network, application and NetApp KPIs relating to the QoS calculations. As all calculations and analysis are executed the resultant outputs will be sent to the QoS/E engine for storage and possible publication to the set of subscribed applications external to the engine.

C. QoE prediction & control manager

This section covers the QoE prediction methodology that is leveraged by the QoE prediction & control manager. QoE prediction is leveraged in Video Quality Assessment (VQA) to measure video quality, with subjective (e.g., a panel of users that perform scoring) or objective methods that essentially predict how the video quality will be perceived by end users.

1) QoE prediction methodology

The proposed approach seeks to capture nuanced phenomena of video streaming QoE prediction, such as the observation that reducing startup delays has little effect on the QoE, or that, once the playback is started, the QoE is more sensitive to time-varying video quality and playback interruptions [3].

The proposed scheme offers the following advantages with respect to existing solutions:

1. It does not require dedicated services running on the client.
2. It does not introduce additional complexity to the client side.
3. It does not suffer from lag due to the delays caused by the feedback channel.

In our QoE prediction model, we consider three entities, namely the Content Distribution Server (CDS), the network/internet and the client. The CDS can retrieve information from two sources, i.e., visual information encoded in different versions of the same video and up-to-date network parameters. Regarding the visual content, the server has access to different versions which are created using different compression parameters on the H.264 standard. To produce these compressed streams, the original videos were compressed using FFmpeg. Regarding the network parameters, these include throughput, rebuffering duration and stalling events. Effectively, in our scheme, the server has access to different versions of compressed videos and can be provided with near real-time information related to network conditions to estimate users’ QoE.

In the case of visual features, we consider the PatchVQ [4] model comprising three stages: (i) spatio-temporal feature extraction; (ii) feature pooling; and (iii) temporal regression. Spatio-temporal feature extraction is achieved by considering four scales for each video sequence, namely the entire sequence (full video), spatially localised features (sv-patch), temporally localised features (tv-patch) and spatiotemporally localised features (stv-patch).

In all cases, feature extraction is performed through Residual Network (ResNet) and Region-Based CNN (R-CNN) models. Both ResNet and R-CNN are CNN-based object detection architectures. CNNs are specific DNN architectures composed of several convolution layers followed by fully connected ones [5].

In this paper, regarding spatial features, we consider the features extracted from PaQ-2-PiQ network [4], a multiscale extension of the 2D ResNet-18 network architecture, which was pre-trained on the LIVE-FB dataset. Furthermore, spatio-temporal features were extracted using a 3D ResNet-18 architecture [6], in which case the model was pre-trained on the Kinetics dataset [7].

The extracted features are fed into the Inception Time model [8]. The Inception Time component consists of several blocks containing parallel convolutions that are different from each other in terms of filter length. The outputs of these convolutions are then combined by a concatenation layer. Two layers are added after the Inception Time blocks, i.e., a Global Average Pooling (GAP) layer and a fully connected layer with a softmax activation function.

For the final prediction of the QoE score, the following are considered: (i) video features (i.e., video bitrate, frame rate and QP values); and (ii) network information (i.e., current network throughput). The relations between the MOS and the provided streaming information is inferred by adding two more fully connected layers (FC1, FC2).

IV. SIGNALING APIS FOR DYNAMIC QoS/QoE ADAPTATION

As the QoS/E Monitoring Engine is executing its analysis there is a wealth of data available to the users that can be observed and used to inform about the results being generated by the engine itself. To make this data available along with the results from the engines' analysis the signaling interface can be used. This is implemented as a Rest API that can be utilised by the various components of the test applications being executed (vertical application, NetApps, UEs, etc.) to allow them to reconfigure their operational parameters based on the calculated outputs from the QoS/E engine. This signaling APIs allow, for example, the NetApps and/or the vertical applications to proactively adapt their performance to avoid stalling that would result in severely degrading the perceived QoE.

A. Architecture

The design of the signaling interface will support two main modes of operation: request based, subscription based. For the request-based approach the engine shall service client requests directly as soon as the request has been issued in order to gather the required data and publish the response to the client. This is the normal client-server type of approach and is triggered purely by a client request being received. For the subscription-based approach the client can register for updates for specific information directly with the Rest API. As results are generated the design of the interface will gather the appropriate results and publish them directly to the clients.

B. Interfaces

The signaling interface for the QoS/E engine will have the ability to service a vast set of requests originating from a

variety of sources such as the following: Vertical applications, NFVIs, UEs, NetApps. As the QoS/E also provides an analysis engine for a vast set of KPIs it would also be feasible that the set of requests that the interface would have to support would be quite large therefore the technology behind the implementation will utilise the GraphQL framework. GraphQL is a technology developed by Facebook to combat the creation of very big and detailed REST APIs that try to cover every possible request that a client may want to make. Instead, it presents as a single REST API interface and the client creates a query for the data it wants back from the server or the data it is sending to the server. GraphQL is a query language for your API, and a server-side runtime for executing queries by using a type system you define for your data. GraphQL isn't tied to any specific database or storage engine and is instead backed by the existing code and data. This will help to reduce the complexity of the interface design as well as future proofing the interface by only having to add new queries to the client requests instead of having to update & rebuild the exposed API interfaces.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The main focus of this work is to describe the design and architecture of the Quality of Service/Quality of Experience Monitoring Engine proposed by the 5GMediaHUB project. The various approaches for data processing utilised for each of the applications sub-components has also been included along with their designs. This paper presents the reader with the information allowing them to understand both the design and functionality of the QoS/E engine and how it can be utilised to facilitate the testing of the applications. It also gives details relating to the design, implementation and testing of the quality of experience prediction components

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